

Peers Alley Media

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5th Edition of
**Advanced
Chemistry
World Congress**

March 25-26, 2024 | Amsterdam, Netherlands

Adv. Chemistry 2024

<https://advanced-chemistry.peersalleyconferences.com/>

PROGRAM-AT-A-GLANCE >>

**YOUR FIRST CHOICE
FOR RESEARCH
INGENUITY**

ADV. CHEMISTRY 2024

DAY 2

MARCH 26, 2024

Scientific Program

07:40-08:25 Registrations

08:25-08:40 Introduction

Moderator: Giovanni Sansoe, Gradenigo Hospital, Torino, Italy

Topics: Analytical Chemistry | Industrial Chemistry | Agricultural Chemistry | Medicinal Chemistry | Chemical Engineering | Green Chemistry | Environmental Chemistry | Biochemistry | Organic Chemistry | Physical Chemistry | Geochemistry | Food Chemistry | Materials Science | Molecular Biology | Polymer Chemistry and Technology

Distinguished Speaker Talks

Session Chair **Sharadha Sambasivan, Suffolk County Community College, USA**

Session Chair **Beena Mathew, Mahatma Gandhi University, India**

08:40-09:00

Title: Solubility of fluorite in concentrated electrolyte solutions at elevated temperatures: Implications to nuclear waste-form development and rare earth element (REE) extraction

Yongliang Xiong, Sandia National Laboratories (SNL), USA

09:00-09:20

Title: Water quality evaluation and impact of nitrogen contamination
Sharadha Sambasivan, Suffolk County Community College, USA

09:20-09:40

Title: Conformational changes of human stratum corneum lipids by effect of cyclic and linear siloxanes

Krystyna Pieńkowska, Medical University of Gdańsk, Poland

09:40-10:00

Title: Montmorillonite-based chitosan nanocomposites as sustainable slow-release green fertilizers

Punnama Siriphannon, King Mongkut's Institute of Technology Ladkrabang, Thailand

10:00-10:20

Title: Graphene assisted optical tweezers and its applications

Yuquan Zhang, Shenzhen University, China

10:20-10:40

Title: Polyol-based extraction: A green approach to extract bioactive compounds for cosmetic and tropical products

Nuntawat Khat-udomkiri, Mae Fah Laung University, Thailand

Group Photo 10:40-10:50

Refreshment Break 10:50-11:05

11:05-11:25

Title: Synthesis and molecular structure studies of Aluminium (III) complexes with β -ketoiminate and ethanolamine ligands

Leonardo Santoni, University College London (UCL), UK

11:25-11:45

Title: Advanced insights into phenylpropene biosynthesis in *Ocimum basilicum* L.: The role of vermicompost form, dose, and application method

İlker TÜRKAY, Kırşehir Ahi Evran University, Turkey

11:45-12:05

Title: Electrical conductivity, microstructures, chemical compositions, and systematic multivariable models to evaluate the effect of waste slag smelting (pyrometallurgical) on the compressive strength of concrete

Ahmed Salih Mohammed, American University of Iraq Sulaimani, Iraq

12:05-12:25

Title: Tumor cell adhesion and metastasis signaling: Contribution of endothelium nitric oxide

Fabiola Sánchez, Universidad Austral de Chile, Chile

12:25-12:45

Title: CdO nanostructures as acid-base bifunctional heterogeneous catalysts for making Coumarin-3- Carboxylic Acids at room temperature

Rupinder Kaur, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Mohali, India

Group Photo 12:45-12:55

Lunch Break 12:55-13:35

Session Chair

Beena Mathew, Mahatma Gandhi University, India

Session Chair

Jen-Chang Yang, Taipei Medical University, Taiwan

13:35-13:55

Title: Composition and characterisation of ancient lime mortar of 12th century temple, Alandi, India

Sarvesh Singh, Reserve Bank of India Archives, India

DISTINGUISHED SPEAKER TALKS

DAY 2

5th Edition of

**ADVANCED
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WORLD
CONGRESS**

**March 25-26, 2024
Amsterdam, Netherlands**

Advanced insights into phenylpropene biosynthesis in *Ocimum basilicum* L.: The role of vermicompost form, dose, and application method

İlker Türkay¹ and Lokman Öztürk²

¹Kırşehir Ahi Evran University, Turkey

²Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa Üniversitesi, Turkey

In this study, we explored the impact of vermicompost on phenylpropanoid metabolism in basil's Peltate glandular trichomes (PGTs). We tested 0, 10%, and 25% doses of solid and tea forms of vermicompost on the methylchavicol chemotype of basil. Gene expression (*PAL*, *4CL*, *EGS*, *EOMT*, *CVOMT*) and phenylpropene accumulation (eugenol, chavicol, methyleugenol, methylchavicol) were analyzed post-treatment. Solid vermicompost (SV) at 10% and 25% doses significantly reduced *EOMT* and *CVOMT* expression and decreased methyleugenol and methylchavicol levels by up to 76% and 52%, respectively. Conversely, 10% vermicompost tea (VT) significantly increased chavicol and methyleugenol levels by 243% and 613%, respectively, and upregulated *EOMT* and *CVOMT* expression. A 25% VT dose also increased eugenol and methylchavicol levels while down regulating the same genes. Our findings indicate that VT modulates phenylpropene accumulation through gene regulation, enhancing basil's aroma and antimicrobial properties. This study underscores the utility of PGTs in plant secondary metabolism research and the potential of vermicompost in phytoremediation.

Biography

Dr. İlker Türkay is an academician and biologist with a focus on the biochemistry of medicinal and aromatic plants, phenylpropanoid metabolism, and plant systematics. Holding a Ph.D. in Biochemistry and an M.Sc. in Plant Taxonomy, he currently serves as a Lecturer at Kırşehir Ahi Evran University. His prior roles include Practicing Expert at the Faculty of Agriculture and Medical Representative for international pharmaceutical firms. Dr. Türkay's unique blend of academic and commercial experience equips him with a nuanced understanding of both scientific research and its real-world applications. Passionate about educating the next generation of scientists, he is committed to contributing to academic and scientific communities through research and collaboration.